

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	2010	B		Min: 63.19 Max: 63.51	1226 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic

In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1272-1273	Photo Model: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 172
---	---	--	---

DEFINITION Wall dividing rooms 4 and 5	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1160	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
---	--	---------------------------------------	---

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
--	---

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
<input type="checkbox"/> Tiles	<input type="checkbox"/> Travertine	<input type="checkbox"/> Ash	
<input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones	
<input type="checkbox"/> Dolia	<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt	<input type="checkbox"/> Human bones	
<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Clay	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth	
<input type="checkbox"/> Mortar	<input type="checkbox"/> Sand	<input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth	
<input type="checkbox"/> Coins	<input type="checkbox"/> Silt	<input type="checkbox"/> Shells	
<input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris	<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		
<input type="checkbox"/> Glass			
			Compaction
			Color
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard
			<input type="checkbox"/> Compact
			<input type="checkbox"/> Friable
			<input type="checkbox"/> Loose
			<input type="checkbox"/> Soft
			<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown
			<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown
			<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White
			<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red
			<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow
			<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)	Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	height: (was obviously higher before abandonment)
Southern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by: 1222	Abuts: Wall 1217
Is covered by:	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1236

OBSERVATIONS: Dividing wall between rooms 4 and 5. Abuts wall 1217 on North side and almost reaches wall 1187 on the south.

DESCRIPTION: Position within sector: Between room 4 x 5. Northern half of Area B.
Shape: Linear, stretching North-South.

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions):
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: South-North

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) 8x10x6 cm Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains: Remaining blocks (south) L=72cm/W=48cm/h=25cm Total wall L=195cm/W=48cm/h=5cm

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Few visible remaining Ashlar blocks running North-South → visible ones situated on the South - few inclusions - few tiles + tufo slag - wall seems to be built before the floor as there is no visible ditch cut in the floor of room 4 x 5.
 Wall standing on bedrock - fine layer of sandy soil between blocks and between Ashlar blocks & bedrock.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by MORGANE

on 29.07.2010

Revised by CPM

on 29.07.2010

PDFd by

on

Entered by

on